

Application of a New Efficient Normal Parameter Reduction Algorithm of Soft Sets in Online Shopping

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Abstract : A new efficient normal parameter reduction algorithm of soft set in decision making was proposed. However, up to the present, few documents have focused on real-life applications of this algorithm. Accordingly, we apply a New Efficient Normal Parameter Reduction algorithm into real-life datasets of online shopping, such as Blackberry Mobile Phone Dataset. Experimental results show that this algorithm is not only suitable but feasible for dealing with the online shopping.

Keywords : soft sets, parameter reduction, normal parameter reduction, online shopping

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